

VISUALIZATION IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING

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Annotation: The article examines the role of the principle of visibility and analyzes effective ways of using visualization of educational material in an English lesson.

Keywords: visualization, English language teaching, multimedia presentation, infographics, mental map.

Introduction.

The problem of motivation to learn English at school not only does not lose its relevance, but, on the contrary, every year it is updated with a number of issues that need to be addressed in order to increase the effectiveness of the learning process. One of the ways to increase motivation is to visualize the material as an active learning practice. This is evidenced by numerous articles and materials presented at educational forums and in electronic pedagogical journals [1,2,12]. The term "visualization" means a change in the form of presentation of information without violating its content, that is, systematization and ordering of the material for its presentation in graphic or other form [11].

According to the modern order of the society, the search for optimal ways of organizing the educational process, as well as rational options for the content of training and its structure requires modern visualization methods, the special role of which is not only the result of the development of technologies that simplify the search and access to information, but also the need for rapid learning and memorization of large volumes of material.

The main purpose of using any method of visual demonstration of educational material is the possibility of implementing two-channel communication, and, accordingly, increasing the volume of transmitted information [10]. The language material becomes compact and devoid of unnecessary details, which allows students to spend less time memorizing it. For the same reason, the fear of a large amount of information for assimilation disappears, which leads to increased motivation. The clarity of the structure of the visualized material and its ergonomics simplify the process of perception. These visualization properties

are especially useful when introducing new vocabulary, as they positively affect the language guess of students, develop it, which acquires an exceptional role if we are talking about a phenomenon with which schoolchildren are not familiar. Visualization meets the principles and requirements of personality-oriented learning, activates the thinking of students, corresponds to the age characteristics of students, and is also suitable for independent work and work with students with disabilities (in particular students with dyslexia) [6]. It helps not only to involve students in the educational process, but also to use modern ICT tools, which play a special role in foreign language education at the present stage of its development [8].

The study of the literature devoted to modern methods of increasing motivation in a foreign language lesson at school through the visualization of information allowed us to identify such methods as:

- 1) multimedia presentation;
- 2) interactive quiz;
- 3) infographics [3].

In the methodology, such methods of ordering educational material are called active learning [4], defined by A.A. Verbitsky as a transition from algorithmized methods of organizing the didactic process to research, developing and contributing to creative and motivating learning [9].

For example, the use of multimedia presentations, that is, slides containing brief and structured information on a specific topic, is one of the main requirements for the use of modern technologies in the classroom. Multimedia presentations are their more innovative version, as they additionally include the use of dynamics, sound, and images, combining a number of aspects that allow you to most effectively hold the listener's attention. Multimedia presentations are characterized by greater visibility of the material provided. They are the material creatively adapted by the teacher for a certain age of students.

To date, multimedia presentations are one of the most effective and frequently used ways to provide educational material, since almost every teacher has the skills to create and integrate them into the educational process.

Multimedia presentation can be used in teaching all aspects of the language, i.e. phonetics, vocabulary and grammar, as well as at different stages of learning, for example, when introducing new material or controlling its assimilation. This type of material provision is able to activate all types of speech activity (listening, speaking, reading and writing).

An interactive quiz, that is, a presentation game saturated with various visualization elements, is effective due to its gaming orientation. This is due to the fact that the game creates the mental tension necessary for any student, while revealing it through active, creative and exciting activities.

This type of work in the classroom corresponds to three main goals, that is, educational (for example, information about the country of the language being studied, the introduction of new vocabulary), developmental (consolidation of knowledge, analysis and evaluation of visual images) and educational (teamwork).

Another effective way of presenting information graphically is infographics or information graphics. The main goal here is to quickly and clearly convey a large amount of information using diagrams, drawings, brief comments and graphs, so this visualization method is especially suitable for the introduction, consolidation or generalization of lexico-grammatical or linguo-cultural material [7].

It is these criteria that characterize infographics as a complex process that requires careful study of information and consideration of a large number of details. However, the complexity of this visualization method is justified by the increased motivation of students, which is caused by the combination of bright design of text content and the presence of figurative and symbolic objects that require guesswork [7]. For example, this technology can be successfully used when working out tenses, prepositions, idiomatic expressions. The compactness of the schemes allows you to use them in the classroom and as a handout.

Another way of visualization is a mental map or memory card, which allows you to depict objects and connections between them for better memorization. Most often, it is used to study the vocabulary or grammar of a foreign language.

Like multimedia presentations, memory cards can be used at any stage of learning a foreign language – when introducing new material, semanticizing or activating it, generalizing, organizing the search for a solution to a problem. But most often teachers use this method when they first get acquainted with the language material and analyze its key ideas. Mental maps can be used to organize group or independent work in the classroom, work with dictionaries, activate the creative and intuitive abilities of students [5]. Each of the visualization methods presented in the article is directly aimed at improving the motivation of students to learn English at school.

The search for new ways of presenting information in a concise and accessible form, the rapid pace of learning associated with the development of new trends

in teaching methods, as well as the availability of modern technologies, their popularity and demand among students determine the relevance of the problem of visualization in English language teaching.

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